

Postdoc Appreciation Week Germany

Toolkit for PIs, Group Leaders and Professors

Introduction

This year marks the fifth Postdoc Appreciation Week in Germany, celebrating five years of collective commitment to raising the visibility and profile of postdoctoral researchers within the German research landscape. This milestone highlights the increasing institutional engagement and ongoing dialogue regarding postdoctoral career development and research culture!

We strongly believe that postdocs in Germany deserve more attention, visibility, and support given their key role in the German academic system – and their difficult working conditions and career prospects coupled with an often very one-dimensional evaluation culture.

We have created this toolkit to give professors, team leaders, and PIs guidance and good practice examples, to thank and support postdocs for their great work.

How to participate in the Postdoc Appreciation Week

Online Campaigns

To establish the Postdoc Appreciation Week more firmly in the scientific community and to promote it to a wider audience, we are organizing a social media campaign ourselves via [LinkedIn](#) during the week and are inviting you to participate. *Post, share and retweet our campaign materials before and during the PAW!*

We have also prepared materials that you can use to create posts (logos and banners). Please write to paw-germany@gast.gwdg.de if you would like to use our materials. You can of course also prepare and use your own materials as well using your regular designs and branding.

Do you have a social media profile? **From our experience, the postdocs greatly appreciate when the PIs create and share their posts of appreciation on social media during PAW.** As an inspiration, we suggest some questions you may want to answer as part of your posts/videos.

- Feel free to use your social media channels as well as your website or a press release to share how important postdocs are for you and how you support them!
- Introduce active, dedicated postdocs in your group! Who contributes innovative and new research ideas? Who is committed to improving the quality of research or the research culture? Who is a dedicated team player and cares for the development of others? Who contributes to broader society or other research users?

- Which challenges do you see when supporting postdocs? What are your ideas on how this can be improved? What's your take on the debates about career perspectives and the insecure situation of postdocs?

The German campaign is connected by our LinkedIn Account as well as via the Hashtag #PAWde or #PostdocAppreciationWeek. Please tag us and use the hashtags to join the campaign. We will be happy to like, share and comment on your contributions from our PAW account.

Local Campaigns

Organizing event/s

Reach out to fellow professors and PIs in your institution and organize a joint social event with your postdocs during PAW! It will provide an excellent networking opportunity for everyone! Of course, a nice and simple gesture of appreciation is to serve food and drink and share a meal together. This also opens up new perspectives and promotes togetherness.

Help the career development of your postdocs and invite e.g., a career counselor from your institution or a role model to give a presentation or a small workshop.

If you are interested in organizing an event, we encourage you to start planning early and to identify colleagues or partners who are willing to support you and your idea. We would love it if you shared the pictures of your in-person events on social media platforms as well!

Promoting the Postdoc Appreciation Week

If you feel comfortable leading the way and promoting open conversations, you can initiate discussion on topics such as authorship practices, power abuse, open science, etc with your postdocs. Of course, the WissZeitVG reform and its influence on postdoc careers can and should be addressed.

We have created a poster that you can share with your postdocs and around your institution, and in that way encourage everyone to participate in the Postdoc Appreciation Week.

The most important thing: express appreciation and recognition for the work of postdocs!

For more information about the PAW and the coordinating team: <https://paw-germany.de/>

If you have questions or comments, please contact us via paw-germany@gast.gwdg.de